

USE OF DIGITALIZATION AND TECHNOLOGY IN THE TRAINING OF ARTISTIC GYMNASTICS SPORTS SPECIALISTS.

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Annotation. This article covers the scientific and methodological foundations of the use of digitalization and modern technologies in the process of training artistic gymnastics sports professionals. The study analyzed the impact of video analysis, biomechanical monitoring, artificial intelligence, and digital learning platforms on training effectiveness. The study also explored the possibilities of improving athletes' technical training, developing digital competencies of coaches, and individualizing training loads. The results of the study showed that digital technologies are an important factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of training of rhythmic gymnastics specialists.

Keywords. Rhythmic gymnastics, digitization, innovative technologies, video analysis, biomechanical monitoring, artificial intelligence, sports training, digital competence, sports pedagogy, training effectiveness.

Аннотация. В статье освещены научно-методические основы использования цифровых технологий и современных технологий в процессе подготовки специалистов по художественной гимнастике. Результаты исследования показали, что цифровые технологии являются важным фактором повышения качества и эффективности подготовки специалистов по художественной гимнастике. Ключевые слова Художественная гимнастика, цифровизация, инновационные технологии, видеанализ, биомеханический мониторинг, искусственный интеллект, спортивная подготовка, цифровая компетентность, спортивная педагогика, эффективность тренировок. фактором повышения качества и эффективности подготовки специалистов по художественной гимнастике.

Ключевые слова. Художественная гимнастика, цифровизация, инновационные технологии, видеанализ, биомеханический мониторинг, искусственный интеллект, спортивная подготовка, цифровая компетентность, спортивная педагогика, эффективность тренировок.

Relevance – problem statement, literature review, and identification of unresolved issues In the modern sports system, digitalization processes are becoming increasingly important in all sports, including FIG Rhythmic Gymnastics. Information and communication technologies, artificial intelligence,

video analytics, biomechanical monitoring, and digital control systems are helping to improve the effectiveness of athlete training. Artistic gymnastics, in particular, requires the widespread introduction of innovative technologies as a sport that requires complex coordination movements, aesthetic expression, and technical accuracy. In recent years, the number of scientific studies on the use of digital technologies in the system of training sports professionals has been increasing. Research has covered issues such as digital monitoring of training, biomechanical analysis of movements, and the development of coach and athlete competencies through online learning platforms [1, 2]. The use of video analysis technologies in sports training is also seen as an effective tool for identifying technical errors and quickly eliminating them [3]. However, an analysis of available scientific sources shows that the methodological foundations of digitalization in the process of training sports professionals in rhythmic gymnastics have not been sufficiently developed. There is a lack of scientific and practical recommendations, especially on the formation of digital competencies of trainers, the implementation of technical analysis systems based on artificial intelligence, and individual modeling of training. Therefore, deepening scientific research in this area is an urgent issue.

Purpose, methods and research organization

The purpose of the research is to scientifically substantiate the effectiveness of the use of digitalization and modern technologies in the training of artistic gymnastics sports professionals. The following methods were used in the research process:

- analysis of scientific and methodological literature;
- pedagogical observation;
- video analysis;
- biomechanical analysis;
- comparative and statistical analysis methods.

The study was conducted over the period 2025–2026 with the participation of rhythmic gymnastics coaches and students working in sports schools and higher education institutions. A total of 24 coaches and 36 female athletes participated in the study. Digital monitoring systems, mobile applications, and video analysis platforms were used during the training sessions.

Research results and their discussion

The results of the study showed that the use of digital technologies in the training of artistic gymnastics sports professionals significantly increases the effectiveness of training. With the help of videoanalysis systems, the amplitude of

movement of athletes, coordination accuracy and the quality of the performance of technical elements were analyzed. As a result, the process of detecting and correcting technical errors by trainers has become much faster. The use of biomechanical monitoring tools in training made it possible to control the functional state of athletes. This helped to individualize the loadings as well as prevent over-fatigue. The study evaluated the accuracy of the elements performed through video platforms powered by artificial intelligence and developed individual recommendations for athletes. Analyzes have shown that digital technologies also improve the methodological activities of trainers. Through online platforms, the possibility of strengthening theoretical knowledge, organizing distance seminars and studying international experiences has expanded. At the same time, it was found that digitization increases athletes' motivation and increases interest in the training process. The results obtained confirm the high efficiency of introducing innovative technologies into the sports education system. In particular, in rhythmic gymnastics, due to the technical complexity and aesthetic requirements, video analytics and digital monitoring systems have emerged as important methodological tools.

Conclusions – with a perspective for further research Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Digitalization in the training of artistic gymnastics sports professionals increases the effectiveness of training;
- video analysis and biomechanical monitoring improve the quality of technical training;
- digital technologies are an effective tool for developing the professional competence of trainers;
- Artificial intelligence-based systems are important in developing individual training programs.

It is advisable to expand scientific research on the use of virtual reality, neurotechnologies, and adaptive control systems based on artificial intelligence in future rhythmic gymnastics training.

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